

Mechanical, Thermal, and Electrical Properties of Woven Laminated Advanced Composites Containing Aligned Carbon Nanotubes

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SUMMARY

Multifunctional properties of a hybrid composite comprised of aligned carbon nanotubes (CNTs) grown *in situ* on woven fibers and a thermoset polymer matrix are characterized. The small volume fraction of CNTs (<3%) enhance laminate performance in three areas: interlaminar strength (x1.7) and Mode I fracture toughness (x1.6), electrical conductivity ($\times 10^6$ - 10^8), and thermal properties (x1.8).

Keywords: Carbon nanotubes, nanocomposites, hybrid composites, polymer-matrix composites (PMCs), interfacial strength, interlaminar fracture

ABSTRACT

Fabrication and multifunctional characterization of a hybrid composite architecture of aligned carbon nanotubes (CNTs) grown *in situ* on fibers infiltrated with a thermoset polymer matrix are reported. The composite is processed via hand lay-up and is comprised of woven alumina fibers, aligned CNTs, and a two-part epoxy matrix. The aligned CNTs at low volume fraction (~1-3 %) enhance multifunctional laminate performance in three dimensions, as evidenced by improvement in interlaminar strength (70% increase) and Mode I fracture toughness (~60% increase), electrical conductivity in the in-plane ($\times 10^6$) and through-thickness ($\times 10^8$) directions, and thermal properties (~80% increase in through-thickness direction). The focus of this paper is presentation of new characterization work particularly in the area of non-mechanical properties, such as thermal and electrical conductivities.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) can be potentially organized into current aerospace structural composites to enhance multiple (structural, electrical, thermal, etc.) properties. Traditional advanced composites has been reported to reduce the structural mass of aerospace vehicles by up to ~50 % compared with metals (aluminum, etc.) [1]. Still, improvements are desired in multi-functional properties; interlaminar shear strength against delamination, electrical conductivity, and thermal conductivity. Through-thickness mechanical properties, particularly at lamina interfaces, require improvement

for aerospace application, since their damage tolerance can limit designs. As another example, electrical conductivity is enhanced by metal layers or metal-coated layers for composite aircraft structures to discharge lightning current away from critical areas or to shield against electromagnetic (EM) interference from high power transmitters [2, 3]. Instead of this added metal layer (additional $\sim 0.4 \text{ kg/m}^2$ [4]), carbon nanotubes are a potential alternative with minimum weight addition due to their high mass-specific properties.

Hybridizing advanced composites using aligned CNTs, can improve multi-functional properties (interlaminar toughness, thermal and electrical properties, and impact tolerance [5]). Due to their unique atomic structures, CNTs have multiple exceptional properties; high mechanical stiffness and strength, and thermal ($\sim 3000 \text{ W/mK}$ [6, 7]) and electrical (just quantum conductance if ideal [8]) conductivities comparable to, or higher than, those of metals [9], especially when normalized by mass due to their low bulk density ($\sim 1.4 \text{ mg/mm}^3$ for SWNTs) [10]. CNT hybrid composites consist ideally of three phases (CNTs, advanced fibers, and matrix) and have only recently been developed, *e.g.*, [11-17]. The nano-engineered composites studied here maintain CNT *alignment* within the bulk aligned-fiber composites in order to take advantage of intrinsic and scale-dependent properties of the CNTs. The two designs of nano-engineered composites investigated are “nano-stitched” composites with aligned CNTs at ply interfaces for mechanical reinforcement (toughness enhancement through bridging) [11, 15], and fuzzy fiber reinforced plastics (FFRPs) with radially aligned CNTs grown on advanced fibers for mechanical (intralaminar and interlaminar) reinforcement and to create thermal and electrical conductive pathways (see Fig. 1) [12]. In this paper, the latter composite (FFRP) is studied. Dense and uniform aligned CNTs are grown directly on aluminum oxide (Al_2O_3) ceramic fiber surfaces of woven cloths using thermal chemical vapor deposition (CVD) (Fig. 1a) [18]. The fuzzy cloths plies are assembled by hand lay-up and infiltrated with room temperature curable epoxy (West Systems, Resin 105 and Hardener 206) driven by capillarity (Fig. 1b) [12]. A detailed study on composite quality (void fraction and constituent volume fraction, V_f) based on single-walled nanotube (SWNT) density [10] can be found elsewhere [11]. Aluminum oxide fibers are chosen as the substrate due to its compatibility with CNT growth as previously confirmed [17]. Furthermore, this model system allows study of the FFRP architecture for application with glass or carbon fiber reinforced plastics (GFRPs and CFRPs). Significant challenges still exist in growing CNTs on carbon fibers without significant damage to the carbon surface [19-21] and tensile property degradation; whereas no damage to the fibers was observed in this alumina-fiber FFRP system during single-fiber tensile testing [16, 17]. In this work, a complete set of FFRP properties are experimentally characterized and summarized (Table 1), together with baseline composites (without CNTs) for comparison, to better understand the effect of CNTs on a broad set of multifunctional properties including new results on electrical and thermal conductivity. Although not discussed here, exposure studies during manufacturing and machining of the FFRP composites has also been investigated to better understand environmental health and safety of these new composites [22-24].

Figure 1. Fuzzy fiber reinforced plastics: a) micro-structure illustration (not to scale), b) cross-sectional schematic to show inter- and intra-ply CNT network and capillary-driven wetting [12] (not to scale), and c) optical image of baseline (top) and FFRP (bottom) composites (3-ply thick) for tensile testing.

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

A variety of mechanical tests have been and are being performed on baseline and FFRP specimens to characterize properties (Table 1). Short beam shear strength was measured on FFRP samples (2.5 mm x 5 mm x 15 mm, 4 ply, ~0.6-2.9 % CNT V_f) using a standard 3-point bending test (Instron 8848 Micro-Tester, 2 kN load cell) based on ASTM D2344, resulting in ~70 % improvement in interlaminar shear strength compared with baseline laminates [12]. Mode I fracture toughness was tested on FFRP samples (150 mm x 25.4 mm x 254 mm, 4 ply with 5.0 mm-long initial pre-crack) using standard double-cantilevered beam (DCB) tests (Zwick Z050, 500 N load cell) based on ASTM D-5528. Tests indicate the initiation and steady-state Mode I interlaminar toughness (G_{Ic} and G_{IR}) are improved by ~60% due to CNT bridging [25]. A closed-form model exploring improvements in fracture toughness due to aligned CNTs at the

interface has been developed [15]. By incorporating different failure modes of CNT reinforcement, upper and lower bounds of steady-state toughness enhancement have been determined for the FFRP architecture [26]. Another ongoing mechanical characterization includes tension bearing tests (ASTM D5961). The post-test samples are shown in Fig. 2. A new method to manufacture FFRPs, resin transfer molding (RTM), is also pursued for relatively large samples used in mechanical characterization, aiming to enhance specimen quality further. Successful manufacturing yielding virtually no voids has recently been demonstrated [27, 28].

Fig 2. Optical images of a) baseline and b) CNT-hybrid (FFRP) composites after tension-bearing mode tests showing different modes of failure (marked with circles).

ELECTRICAL PROPERTIES

Electrical property characterization of FFRPs are further pursued to follow up and complete previous work (Table 1) [12, 29]. Silver paint (Structures Probe Inc.) was applied by hand to the relevant surfaces of the composite as electrodes for measurement in both the through-thickness and in-plane directions. The residual impedance of the experimental setup was accounted for by separately measuring the silver paste electrodes, and was eliminated from the sample measurements by subtraction. The previously measured DC resistances [12] were analyzed with percolation theory. New samples for AC impedance measurement are prepared with geometrical uniformity, so that direct data comparison among the set is possible (unlike the previous AC characterization work [29] where measurements required geometric-normalization to interpret the results).

The FFRP samples were previously tested for DC electrical conductivity. The conductivity increase by a factor of 10^6 - 10^8 with just ~ 0.5 - 3 CNT wt% suggests that a carbon-fiber FFRP “conductive” composite may be employed in future. Here, the measured data are curve-fitted to the simple relation between filler concentration and conductivity [30], $\sigma = \sigma_0 (p - p_c)^t$ where σ_0 is conductivity (saturated) and p_c is the spherical particle concentration (percolation concentration). Although the sample size is small, as shown in Fig. 3a, a percolation threshold is calculated as $\sim 0.56\%$ V_f from an exponent and saturated resistivity of 0.33 and 0.2 Ohm·cm (in-plane), and 0.23 and 2.9 Ohm·cm (through-thickness), respectively. This percolation threshold is comparable to previous work on 2 phase CNT composites (non-aligned CNTs and polymer, minimum

~0.2 weight % of percolation threshold [31, 32]). The exponent values are much smaller than other previous examples (~1.3-4) [32]. Small exponent in the percolation relation can be interpreted as a reduced influence of volume fraction on conductivity increase, and/or a reflection of the unique distribution of aligned and long CNTs inside the FFRPs that contain primarily insulating alumina fibers and epoxy. Details of the electrical conductive pathways in the complex 3-dimensional FFRP nano/microstructure need further study but it is hypothesized as the long CNTs minimize tunneling barrier resistance between each other [32, 33].

A new set of AC samples with consistent geometric sample dimensions are tested, and directly compared without geometrical normalization (since normalization is not necessary). The dimensions of the samples for measurement in the through-thickness (3 ply) and in-plane (5 ply) directions are 3.4 x 7.5 x 12.3 mm and 0.9 x 6.6 x 11.6 mm, respectively. Impedances are measured using an impedance analyzer (HP impedance/gain-phase analyzer 4194A, 10 mV over the frequency range of 10 Hz – 40 MHz). The samples are mounted on the accompanied test fixture (HP 16047C), and electrically connected with copper strips. For each CNT V_f condition, multiple samples are fabricated. Measurements on each sample are repeated for three different points on the electrode surface, yielding consistent and repeatable data. Nyquist diagram examples in the through-thickness direction are shown in Fig. 3b. With a small volume fraction (~ 0.3 % V_f), the impedance shows similar behavior to an ideal parallel R-C circuit (curve-fitted with ~60 Ohm of resistance and ~53 pF of capacitance). With a larger volume fraction (~8.9 % V_f) of CNTs, the resistance decreases (~1.7 Ohm), and capacitance becomes less dominant across the frequency range, converging into a simple resistive equivalent-circuit behavior as shown in Fig. 3b. The conductivities normalized from the AC impedances have the values in the same range (~ $\times 10^{-2}$ S/mm, with ~ 8 % V_f CNT) as the ones obtained from DC measurements reported previously (shown in Table 1).

a)

b)

Figure 3. Electrical properties of FFRPs: a) DC electrical conductivity increase with CNT concentration (curve-fitted with percolation theory) in log scale, and b) Nyquist plot examples of AC impedance measured in the through-thickness direction.

THERMAL PROPERTIES

Thermal conductivities of FFRPs in the through-thickness direction are calculated using the laser-flash method (NETZSCH, microflash LFA457). FFRP samples (1 or 2 ply) are core-drilled and polished down (Struers, $\sim 5 \mu\text{m}$ roughness) to have a ~ 1.25 mm-diameter disc configuration with ~ 1 mm thickness, and are mounted inside the machine. The front side of the sample is heated using a laser pulse (maximum 15 J, 0.33 ms), and the temperature profile on the opposite side of the specimen is measured with an infrared detector over time. Thermal diffusivity is obtained via the time required to cool

down (to half the maximum temperature) and the sample thickness. Heat capacity is measured from the initial temperature increase estimated again from the sample temperature profile over time. Thermal conductivity is calculated as the product of the measured thermal diffusivity and heat capacity and the known specimen density. The data extraction analysis used is for isotropic media and does not take into account differences due to in-plane vs. through-thickness property variation which may be present in the laminated woven FFRP composite. Measured heat capacity has a relatively constant value of ~ 1.1 J/gK regardless of CNT volume fraction, while thermal diffusivity shows a slight increase from 0.3 (baseline) to 0.7 mm²/s (~ 4.4 % V_f CNT). Accordingly, thermal conductivity, with the error range estimated as $< \sim 3$ %, shows ~ 80 % increase with ~ 4.4 % V_f of CNTs, as shown in Fig. 4. In-plane thermal conductivity measurements using a comparator method based on ASTM E1225 are underway.

The calculated thermal conductivity of ~ 0.7 W/mK is rather moderate compared to metals (~ 100 s of W/mK). In addition, the improvement percentage (~ 80 %) is also lower than that of electrical conduction (6 to 8 orders of magnitude). This behavior is attributed to different mechanisms of thermal vs. electrical transport, particularly important are thermal barrier resistances (TBRs) between the CNTs and the other constituents (alumina fibers and epoxy) [5]. Improvement in data extraction is desired to account for heat dissipation in other directions. Concerning the samples, thermal transport may be interrupted by a high boundary resistance (between CNTs and matrices) and the large volume fraction of insulating alumina fibers (~ 40 % V_f) [34]. To achieve the case of continuous CNT bridges resulting in high (~ 100 s of W/mK) thermal conduction [35], structural or chemical modification of the FFRPs can be pursued in the future to obtain an improved thermal CNT network.

Figure 4. Thermal conductivity of FFRP in the through-thickness direction.

Table 1. Multi-functional properties of alumina-FFRP with aligned CNTs.

Property		Baseline	Hybrid (improvement)	CNT V_f (%)
Short beam shear strength (MPa) [12]		20.1 ± 0.9	33.8 ± 1.1 (x1.69)	~1-3
Mode I critical strain energy release rate (kJ/m^2) [26]	G_{Ic}	1.07	1.69 (x 1.58)*	~1
	G_{IR}	1.93	3.10 (x 1.61)*	
DC electrical conductivity (S/ mm) [12]	In-plane	$1.15 \pm 0.82 \times 10^{-7}$	$1.20 \pm 0.17 \times 10^{-1}$ ($\times 10^6$)	~2.7
	Through-thickness	$4.17 \pm 1.34 \times 10^{-10}$	$1.36 \pm 0.17 \times 10^{-2}$ ($\times 10^7$)	
Thermal conductivity (W/mK)		0.36	0.76 ± 0.17 (x2.08)	2.2

* This is for one FFRP specimen that is representative of a larger set of ongoing fracture testing.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The characterized properties of FFRPs, in comparison with baseline composites without CNTs, are summarized in Table 1 along with previous results [12, 29]. With a small volume fraction of CNTs, both the fracture toughness for crack initiation and steady-state fracture toughness exhibit an improvement of 60%, the electrical conductivity is enhanced by 6-8 orders of magnitude, and the thermal conductivity increases by ~80%. Further property characterization work is on-going in multiple directions, including a full set of Mode I (together with model-experiment correlation analysis [26]) and Mode II fracture, tension-bearing, in-plane tensile, and impact tests, among others. In addition, nano-composites (solely aligned CNTs infiltrated with epoxy) are chosen as a representative volume element of the above nano-engineered composites, and have been rigorously studied to better understand the transport phenomena inside and between CNTs. The aligned-CNT architecture can be extended to other matrices for high temperature applications to improve flame resistivity, thermal stability [36], and fire-smoke-toxicity [37]. Applications of this three-dimensional hierarchical CNT-composite with improved electrothermal properties are numerous, from heaters for airplane surface deicing and anti-icing to structural health monitoring.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by Airbus S.A.S., Boeing, Embraer, Lockheed Martin, Saab AB, Spirit AeroSystems, Textron Inc., Composite Systems Technology, and TohoTenax through MIT's Nano-Engineered Composite aerospace Structures (NECST) Consortium, and by the Linda and Richard (1958) Hardy Fellowship. The authors gratefully acknowledge A. John Hart (Univ. of Michigan), John Kane, Gang Chen, Hohyun Lee, and George D. Whitfield for valuable discussion and technical support.

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